

THE NARRATIVES OF THE TEACHERS: LEARNING CLIMATE UNDER THE “BARE WALLS POLICY”

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17997101>

ABSTRACT

This study examined the experiences and perceptions of elementary school teachers regarding the implementation of the Bare Walls Policy (DepEd Order No. 21, s. 2023) at Del Pilar Elementary School in Bohol, focusing on its effects on the learning climate within classrooms. Utilizing narrative inquiry within a descriptive qualitative framework, the research engaged eight Kindergarten to Grade 6 teachers as participants, who were purposefully selected based on their recognized excellence in classroom structuring during the Brigada Eskwela 2022 implementation. Data were collected through semi-structured interviews designed to capture in-depth narratives about teachers' firsthand experiences, perspectives, and adaptations to the policy, particularly in relation to student engagement, attention, and retention of ideas. The findings indicate that the policy represented a significant shift in instructional practices, particularly for younger learners who rely heavily on visual aids and classroom decorations to enhance understanding and maintain interest. Teachers reported that while the policy's intent to reduce distractions and promote focus was appreciated, the absence of visual stimuli presented notable challenges, including diminished student engagement and difficulty in conveying complex concepts. The study further revealed that the implementation of the policy prompted significant changes in teachers' decision-making processes, requiring more creativity, intentionality, and flexibility in lesson preparation and execution. To address these challenges while maintaining policy compliance, teachers suggested several innovations, including allowing temporary or removable visual aids during lessons, providing access to varied and portable learning materials such as laminated charts, flashcards, and digital tools, and implementing professional development programs focused on adaptive teaching strategies. Overall, the study underscores the complex and multifaceted impact of the Bare Walls Policy on the learning climate, encompassing social, psychological,

emotional, and cognitive dimensions of student learning. The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of how educational policies influence classroom environments, teacher practices, and student learning outcomes, emphasizing the importance of contextualized policy implementation and support mechanisms for educators to optimize learning experiences in line with contemporary educational goals.

Keywords: *Bare Walls Policy, learning climate, narrative inquiry, elementary education, teacher perceptions, classroom engagement*

INTRODUCTION

Learning Climate is the overall atmosphere, culture, and environmental factors within an educational setting that shape and influence the learning experience of students. This encompasses the physical, social, emotional, and psychological aspects of the learning environment, including factors such as classroom culture, teacher-student relationships, peer interactions, classroom resources, and the overall emotional tone of the learning space (Fisher et al., 2016).

DepEd Order No. 21, s. 2023, which is known as Brigada Eskwela Implementing guidelines, provides the guidelines for Brigada Eskwela and requires schools to clear school grounds, classrooms, and all its walls of “unnecessary artwork, decorations, tarpaulin and posters.” Vice President and Education Secretary Sara Z. Duterte said in an interview regarding the DepEd Order with the media *ABS-CBN TV Patrol* on August 16, 2023. “Take out everything on the wall. Let Learners focus on their studies. Classrooms and schools should be clean and functional” (Chi, 2023).

The DepEd Bohol division is expected to adhere to DepEd Order No.21, s.2023 and ensure that all schools in the province comply with the “Bare Walls Policy”. Schools in Bohol may need to remove existing decorations, artworks, and posters from classroom walls and other areas.

According to Smith and Karaman (2019), the physical environment within educational settings has a substantial impact on the psychological and cognitive well-being of learners. Furthermore, the absence of visual stimuli, such as educational materials and displays, can potentially influence the engagement and motivation of students, as highlighted by Johnson (2018). Conversely, proponents of the Bare Walls argue that minimalistic classroom settings may alleviate distractions and foster a greater focus on learning (Garcia, 2020). According to Tucker (2017) elements such as wall displays, decorations, and visual aids can positively influence students’ learning outcomes.

These contrasting perspectives underscore the need for an in-depth exploration of the practical implications of the policy in the classroom. Studies on the Bare Walls Policy have shown considerable effects on learning situations. Still, no study investigated the learning climate as narratives from the actual stories of teachers and students.

As educators and learners adapt to this new directive, it becomes imperative to examine the lived experiences and perceptions surrounding the implementation of this policy (Bonghanoy et al., 2024). By employing a narrative inquiry approach, this study endeavors to shed light on the multifaceted implications of the Bare Walls Policy and its role in shaping the learning environment thus informing future discussions and decision-making processes within educational institutions.

Research Questions

This study aimed to bring stories of the actual experiences and perspectives of the teachers embodying the learning climate under DepEd Order No. 21, S. 2023 on “Bare Walls Policy” through Narrative Inquiry.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. How do teachers perceive the Bare Wall Policy?
2. How does the implementation of the policy affect students’ learning behavior in terms of their:
 - 2.1. interactions with teachers or classmates during classes;
 - 2.2. interest or attention during learning activities;
 - 2.3. retention of ideas and understanding of the lessons?
3. What are the important changes in the decision-making process of the teachers in planning and implementing lessons in consideration of the policy?
4. What innovations can be proposed to enrich the learning climate?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research employed narrative inquiry through a descriptive qualitative method to gain a comprehensive understanding of the actual experiences and perceptions of the teachers about the learning climate under the Bare Walls Policy. Semi-structured interviews with participants served as the primary data sources. The participants were the teachers who provided the range of perspectives central to this policy’s effect in social, psychological, emotional, and cultural aspects in the learning environment.

Research Environment

This study was conducted at specific public school within the Bohol Division. The selected school was Del Pilar Elementary School in the municipality of Pilar. The school was chosen based on the recommendation of the District Supervisor, as it was one of the top-performing schools in terms of the implementation of Brigada Eskwela 2022. One notable aspect of its performance was being recognized for excellence in classroom structuring for teachers.

Research Participants

The target participants were the eight (8) Kindergarten to Grade 6 teachers of Del Pilar Elementary School. Creswell suggested five to twenty-five participants (as cited in Mason, 2010). Regarding data saturation—a key principle in qualitative research, particularly within grounded theory—this study is guided by the perspective of Green et al. (2007), who emphasize that saturation is achieved when additional data no longer contribute new insights to the emerging categories or themes. Rather than being determined strictly by sample size, saturation depends on the depth and richness of the collected information. Nonetheless, qualitative methodologists generally acknowledge that studies with a small number of well-selected participants can reach meaningful saturation when the narratives are sufficiently detailed and analytically robust.

Since this study did not follow the quantitative research tradition, which aims for representativeness and generalizability of results, participants were chosen using the purposeful or purposive sampling technique. In qualitative research, purposive sampling was used to select a specific group of individuals or units for analysis. Participants were selected intentionally, not randomly, and based on defined criteria—specifically, that they had all been awarded “Best in Classroom Structuring” during the Brigada Eskwela implementation in 2022. Other schools were excluded based on this criterion.

In the selection process, the researcher sought assistance from the Public School District Supervisor and school principals in identifying potential candidates for the study based on the selection criteria. The researcher ensured that the participants’ anonymity and confidentiality were protected by assigning screen names or codes and carefully handling any sensitive information. Only the researcher had exclusive access to the raw responses provided by the participants.

To recruit participants, the researcher sent a formal letter of request along with the Informed Consent Form and Interview Guide. In the informed consent, it was made clear that participation in the study was voluntary; thus, participants were informed that they could withdraw at any time without fear of punishment or humiliation.

The informed consent also stated that the conversations would be recorded and later transcribed for the purpose of data analysis.

Research Instrument

The qualitative research instrument for this study included a semi-structured interview guide composed of open-ended questions designed to elicit public elementary school teachers’ narrative experiences and perceptions regarding the removal of classroom decorations and their influence on attention and learning outcomes. A semi-structured interview guide was used to gather insights from elementary teachers. This interview aimed to provide a deeper understanding of teachers’ interpretations in responding to changes in the learning environment.

Research Procedure

Before conducting the semi-structured interview, a list of questions was prepared, tailored to the interview topic, and designed to prompt in-depth conversation. A letter of permission to conduct the study was sent to the offices of the Vice President for Academics and the Graduate School Dean. Upon receiving notification from the Dean that the permission had been granted, permission letters were drafted for the Schools Division Superintendent of the Bohol Division and the District Supervisor of Pilar. These endorsements were presented to the selected school. The questionnaire secured approval from the Ethics Review Board of the University.

The next step involved the careful selection of interviewees to ensure the relevance and value of the interview results. Subsequently, informed consent and approval were obtained from the participants prior to the interviews. The interviews were recorded via audio or video, with consent, to ensure accurate transcription and analysis of the data. During the interviews, the interviewer explained the aim of the study and outlined its structure. Interviewees were informed that the interviews would be semi-structured and designed to encourage teachers to share their experiences and perspectives regarding the minimalistic classroom design and its effects on students' attention and learning outcomes.

The researcher followed the steps of narrative analysis as outlined by Clandinin (2006) in the *Handbook of Narrative Inquiry: Mapping a Methodology*. These steps involve determining whether the inquiry is suitable for a narrative approach, selecting one or more individuals who have significant stories to share, collecting these narratives, analyzing and re-storying the accounts, and finally interpreting the findings in order to generate meaningful understandings from participants' lived experiences.

Data Analysis

In the interpretation and analysis of the data, it was analyzed using the six-phase thematic analysis frame worked by Braun and Clarke (2006). Systematic process involved:

Familiarization- Immersing in the data through repeated readings of the transcripts; Initial Coding- Assigning meaningful codes into broader thematic categories; Theme Development- Organizing codes into broader thematic categories; Review and Refinement- Ensuring thematic coherence and eliminating overlap; Theme Definition- Defining and naming themes in accordance to study's objectives; Interpretation- Analyzing themes derive meaning in relation to the research questions and contextual realities.

RESULTS

The data were collected from participants and analyzed using thematic and coding techniques, with the results presented through themes to facilitate a clear and insightful interpretation.

Table 1. Elementary Teachers' Perception of Bare Wall Policy

Themes	Codes	Sample Narratives
A Huge Shift: Challenged the Teaching of Younger Learners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Frustrating • Unimaginable Learning • Limits Teacher's Ability • Overwhelming 	<p>"I found it frustrating. "Honestly, I was skeptical. I thought it might make teaching more challenging, especially for younger students."- MS</p> <p>"I was surprised and honestly frustrated. I couldn't imagine how a plain classroom could create a good learning environment, especially for younger kids who need visuals to stay engaged."-MVD</p> <p>"I felt frustrated and confused. I thought it would limit my ability to make lessons engaging and effective, especially for visual learners."-MAE</p> <p>"At first, it was a bit overwhelming. I've always been someone who uses lots of visuals in the classroom to engage students. So, the policy felt like a huge shift."-MA</p>
Reduced Distraction but Diminished Engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced Distraction-Reduced Learning Stimulation • Good Intention-Impractical • Rigid for Young Learners 	<p>"While I understand the intent to minimize distractions, I think it takes away a vital aspect of classroom learning—the visuals that stimulate curiosity and engagement."-MS</p> <p>"I think the intention is good, but it's not entirely practical. While it aims to reduce distractions, I believe some students, especially younger ones, need visuals to better understand and retain concepts."-MRS</p> <p>"I was surprised and a bit disheartened. I didn't understand how a 'bare' classroom could foster creativity or engagement. I felt like it was taking away something valuable from the learning process."- MRS</p>
Increased Focus	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased Focus on Discussion • Increased Focus in the Lesson 	<p>"Yes, they've changed slightly. I see some benefits, like increased focus during discussions, but still think visuals are necessary for younger learners." -MS</p> <p>I've started to see how a minimalist classroom can encourage students to focus more on the lesson and less on the environment. - MVD</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More Attention 	<p><i>"I initially thought it was a step backward, but over time, I've come to appreciate the discipline it enforces. Students seem to pay more attention to oral instruction, and the policy has forced me to find other ways to engage them."- MC</i></p>
Needs Flexibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not a one-size-fits-all • Depends on Learner's Age and Subject's Difficulty 	<p><i>"While the policy has its merits, it should be more flexible. It's not a one-size-fits-all approach, and teachers need the freedom to use the tools that work best for their students." – MC</i></p> <p><i>"I think the policy needs to be flexible depending on the subject and age of the students. While it works for some subjects, I believe it can be difficult for younger students, especially in subjects like science or math."- MA</i></p>

Table 1 presents the perceptions of elementary school teachers regarding the implementation of the Bare Wall Policy as mandated by DepEd Order No. 21, s. 2023. The data were gathered from qualitative interviews and coded into themes that highlight how teachers respond to and adapt to the new classroom environment without the traditional visual aids posted on the walls. The emerging themes underscore the complex reactions from educators.

This section synthesizes the shared perceptions and experiences of elementary school teachers regarding the implementation of the Bare Wall Policy (BWP) under DepEd Order No. 21, s. 2023. Drawing from qualitative interviews, the findings reflect educators' insights into how the policy affects their teaching strategies, student engagement, and overall classroom dynamics. The responses reveal both positive and negative reactions, highlighting the complexity of adapting to a minimalist classroom environment without the traditional visual aids.

This also presents the emerging themes from the interview data that reflect teachers' perceptions and responses to the Bare Wall Policy. The identified themes include: (1) A Huge Shift: Challenged the Teaching of Younger Learners, (2) Reduced Distraction but Diminished Engagement, (3) Increased Focus, and (4) Needs Flexibility. These themes provide a deeper understanding of the policy's perceived impact and how teachers navigate the demands of a visually minimal classroom.

SYNTHESIS AND THEMATIC DISCUSSION ON THE PERCEPTION OF THE TEACHERS TO “BARE WALLS POLICY”

Theme 1: A Huge Shift: Challenged the Teaching of Younger Learners

Many teachers expressed that the implementation of the Bare Wall Policy represented a major departure from their traditional teaching practices. For educators

accustomed to using colorful and interactive visual aids, the shift was initially met with frustration and disbelief. They emphasized that young learners in particular rely heavily on visual stimuli to remain engaged and grasp concepts more effectively. Teachers feared that without visual materials, their ability to deliver meaningful and enjoyable lessons would be significantly hindered. As one participant put it, the change was “overwhelming” and made it “unimaginable” to maintain a stimulating classroom atmosphere.

This theme is characterized by codes such as frustrating, unimaginable learning, limits teacher’s ability, and overwhelming. These responses reflect a significant sense of disturbance among teachers who were usually use visual aids as part of their teaching strategies. Teachers expressed that younger learner, in particular, need rich visual stimuli to sustain attention and support comprehension. The removal of these visual elements created a perception of decreased teaching efficacy.

This aligns with the findings of Fisher et al. (2016), who emphasize the importance of visual scaffolds in supporting student engagement and memory retention in early education. Classrooms that provide multi-sensory inputs tend to foster more effective learning, especially for younger learners.

Theme 2: Reduced Distraction but Diminished Engagement

While acknowledging the policy’s goal of minimizing distractions, teachers also noted a trade-off reduced stimulation for learning. Several participants believed that visuals do more than just decorate a room; they serve as cognitive tools that help children make sense of abstract ideas. The minimalist classroom, while well-intentioned, was described as impractical for certain age groups. Educators felt that it overlooked the developmental needs of young learners, who often benefit from a visually rich environment to sustain attention and spark curiosity.

Teachers acknowledged the policy's aim of minimizing distractions (reduced distraction-reduced learning stimulation, good intention-impractical, rigid for young learners), but they also observed an unintended decline in student engagement and stimulation. While the policy may promote order, it removes vital tools that naturally draw curiosity and support understanding, especially for younger students who benefit from concrete representations. This concern is reflected in the work of Weinstein and Romano (2014), who argue that while an uncluttered environment can reduce cognitive overload, overly sterile classrooms can hinder motivational and affective learning elements. The challenge lies in balancing clarity and stimulation.

Theme 3: Increased Focus

Despite initial resistance, some teachers eventually recognized benefits in terms of student focus. Participants shared that the absence of wall decorations helped redirect

students' attention to oral discussions and the core lesson content. This was seen as a positive shift toward discipline and deeper engagement with verbal instruction. However, even those who acknowledged these advantages continued to advocate for visual support, especially for students who are visual learners or have shorter attention spans. Interestingly, some teachers observed that the minimalist environment encouraged students to concentrate more on discussions and verbal instruction (increased focus on discussion, increased focus in the lesson, more attention). While this shift was initially met with resistance, it eventually led to adaptations in teaching strategies and a newfound appreciation for oral instruction and classroom discipline.

Barrett et al. (2015) found that classroom design has a direct effect on student learning, and while visual stimuli are crucial, simplicity can enhance focus when paired with effective pedagogical strategies.

Theme 4: Needs Flexibility

A dominant theme across the interviews was the call for flexibility in implementing the policy. Teachers argued that a standardized, one-size-fits-all approach does not account for the diversity of learners' needs and subject matter complexities. Many suggested that the policy should be adaptable based on students' age and the nature of the subject being taught. For instance, subjects that involve abstract thinking, such as science or math, may benefit from supplemental visuals to aid comprehension. Thus, while teachers did not entirely oppose the policy, they advocated for discretion in its application.

Teachers indicated that the policy should not be uniformly applied across all levels and subjects (not a one-size-fits-all, depends on learner's age and subject's difficulty). This theme suggests that while structure is important, pedagogical flexibility is necessary to meet the diverse needs of learners.

A differentiated instruction model advocated by Tomlinson (2017), which stresses the need for instructional strategies that cater to students' varying readiness levels, interests, and learning profiles. Strict uniformity can undermine effective instruction when not adapted to contextual needs.

Table 2. Impact of The Bare Walls Policy to Students' Learning Behavior

Themes	Codes	Sample Narratives
Theme 1: BWP Increased Classroom interaction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased Student-Teacher Interaction Increased Student-Teacher and Student-Student Interactions 	<p><i>"I've noticed students interact more during group activities"-MS</i></p> <p><i>"I've noticed that students interact more during group activities now. They rely more on their classmates and me for clarification instead of looking at the walls for answers."-MVD</i></p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Asked More Questions and Relay on Peers • Relying on Interaction • Less Confident • More Engagement • Relying on Teacher 	<p><i>“Students are more likely to ask questions now, and they rely on their peers more during group activities.</i></p> <p><i>“Some students are less confident because they don’t have visual cues to rely on...- MRF</i></p> <p><i>“I’ve observed that students now rely more on each other during group activities and ask me more questions. It’s a good change in terms of fostering interaction, but for some students struggles without visual aids”. -MT</i></p> <p><i>“Some students are less confident because they don’t have visual cues to rely on...-MRF</i></p> <p><i>‘I’ve noticed more interaction between students. Without the visuals to rely on, they engage with me more and ask questions when they need clarification. They’re also talking more to each other in group discussions’...-MA</i></p> <p><i>“I’ve noticed that students ask more questions now. They rely on me for clarification more than they did before...- MC</i></p>
<p>Theme 2: A Mixed Bag</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Differing Attention • More Focus Less Interest • More Attentive Less-Interested More-Disengaged • Hard to Keep Everyone Engaged • Varying Behavior 	<p><i>“Some students seem to pay more attention during discussions, but others seem less excited about learning.”-MS</i></p> <p><i>“It’s a mixed bag. Some students seem more focused, but others, particularly those who are visual learners, seem to lose interest more quickly.”-MR</i></p> <p><i>“Some students are more attentive because there are fewer distractions, but others, especially those who are visual learners, seem less interested and more disengaged.” MT</i></p> <p><i>“Yes, some students are more attentive, but others seem to struggle without the visual aids they’re used to. It’s harder to keep everyone equally engaged. “...-MAE</i></p> <p><i>“It varies. Some students are more focused because there are fewer distractions, but others, especially those who learn visually, seem to lose interest more quickly...MRF</i></p> <p><i>“Theres been a noticeable difference. Some students are more attentive now because they have fewer distractions, but others seem to lose focus faster. Visual learners, in particular, are struggling a bit more to stay engaged...MA</i></p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More Attentive- Lack focus- Struggle to Engage • More Focused- Disengaged- Fluctuating Interest 	<p><i>"Students seem more focus on the lessons, as there are fewer distractions. However, some of them seem disengaged at times, especially those who learn best through visual aids, Overall, the interest level fluctuates depending on the activity...MC</i></p>
<p>Theme 3: Harder for Difficult Topics</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Harder for Abstract Concepts • Harder for Science or Math • Harder Understanding without Visual Support • Demand More Time • Need Support • Preserved Auditory and Kinesthetic Learners 	<p><i>"For straightforward topics, it's fine. But for more abstract concepts, it's harder for them to grasp without visual aids." MS</i></p> <p><i>"For simple lessons, it's fine, but for more complicated ones, like science or math concepts, it's harder for students to grasp without visual aids. "...-MVD</i></p> <p><i>"For simple topics, it hasn't made much difference. But for more complex lessons, like science and math, students," students seem to have a harder time grasping the material without visual support. MAE</i></p> <p><i>"It has made it harder for some students to grasp complex or abstract topics. Without visuals, I need to spend more time explaining concepts, and even then, some students still struggle to fully understand." MRF</i></p> <p><i>"I think for simpler topics, the policy hasn't had much of an impact. However, for more abstract or complex subjects, I've seen that students need more support to fully understand...-MA</i></p> <p><i>"For students who are more auditory or kinesthetic learners, I've noticed little change—they seem to adapt just fine."-MC</i></p>

Table 2 summarizes the narratives and experiences of elementary school teachers regarding the impact of the Bare Walls Policy (BWP) on students' learning behavior. It addresses the central research question: How does the implementation of the policy affect students' learning behavior, particularly in relation to (1) their interactions with teachers and classmates during classes, (2) their interest or attention during learning activities, and (3) their retention of ideas and understanding of lessons. The findings are drawn from qualitative data and presented through thematic analysis.

This also presents the themes derived from teachers' responses concerning how the BWP has influenced students' learning behavior. The responses were categorized into three major themes: (1) Increased Classroom Interaction, (2) A Mixed Bag, and (3) Harder for Difficult Topics. These themes offer insights into how students are adapting socially and cognitively in a learning environment devoid of traditional visual stimuli.

SYNTHESIS AND THEMATIC DISCUSSION ON THE IMPACT OF THE “BARE WALLS POLICY” TO STUDENTS’ LEARNING BEHAVIOR

Theme 1: BWP Increased Classroom Interaction

This theme highlights that the removal of wall visual aids led to an increase in both student-teacher and peer interactions. Codes such as “Asked More Questions and Rely on Peers”, “Relying on Teacher”, and “More Engagement” suggest that students have shifted their reliance from passive visual materials to active interpersonal communication. Teachers observed that students are more likely to ask questions and depend on collaborative group work, which fosters critical thinking and interpersonal development. While some students showed reduced confidence initially, the trend generally pointed towards deeper classroom engagement through dialogue and interaction.

This aligns with the study of Al-Mashaqbeh & Al-Huneiti (2023) examined how reducing visual distractions in classrooms can promote more verbal interaction and collaboration among students. Their findings indicated that environments with fewer visual stimuli encouraged students to engage more actively with teachers and peers, increasing question-asking and verbal participation paralleling Vygotsky’s concept of learning through social engagement. “Students became more reliant on peers and instructors for clarification and learning, developing stronger communication and problem-solving skills” (Al-Mashaqbeh & Al-Huneiti, 2023, p. 54).

Theme 2: A Mixed Bag

The second theme captures the varied responses among students to the absence of visual stimuli. Codes like More Attentive Less-Interested, Hard to Keep Everyone Engaged, and Varying Behavior reflect this duality. While some students became more focused due to fewer distractions, others especially visual learners showed signs of disinterest and disengagement. This suggests that BWP’s impact is not uniform and may depend significantly on students’ individual learning preferences.

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Recent studies support this observation. For instance, Cuevas (2015) emphasizes that although learning styles like “visual” or “auditory” may not be as fixed as previously believed, students still respond differently to instructional environments based on cognitive preferences.

Theme 3: Harder for Difficult Topics

This theme reveals that the BWP has disproportionately affected students' ability to learn abstract or complex subjects, especially in Math and Science. Codes such as Struggle with Abstract Ideas and Need Support demand more time, indicate that visual aids were instrumental in helping students understand non-concrete concepts. Teachers expressed that they now spend more time explaining lessons that previously would have been supported by charts or diagrams.

According to Mayer's (2009) Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning, people learn more effectively when words and relevant images are presented together, particularly for complex content. The removal of such visual supports under the BWP contradicts this principle, potentially making it harder for students to construct mental models necessary for abstract reasoning.

Table 3. Changes in the Decision-Making Process of the Teachers

Themes	Codes	Sample Narratives
Theme 1: Teaching Approach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More Intentional & Creative 	<p><i>"It has made me more intentional about planning. I've had to find creative ways to make lessons engaging without relying on posters or charts."</i> MS</p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Storytelling or Role-Playing 	<p><i>"I now use storytelling or role-playing for some topics."</i> MVD</p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Verbal Explanations and Objects 	<p><i>"I've also incorporated more verbal explanations and physical objects into my teaching."</i> MRS</p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engaging Lessons 	<p><i>"It has made lesson planning more challenging. I have to think carefully about how to make the lessons engaging and clear without relying on visuals."</i> MT</p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interactive Lessons 	<p><i>"I focus on interactive lessons and group work to keep the students engaged. I also use handouts and the whiteboard more often for illustrations and diagrams."</i> MT</p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Small Group Activities 	<p><i>"I've started using small group activities more often. For example, during a math lesson, I use physical objects like blocks or coins for demonstrations. I've also incorporated games that encourage participation."</i> MAE</p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More Physical /Hands on Materials 	<p><i>"I've incorporated more physical materials into my lessons. For instance, in math, I use objects like blocks or counters to explain equations. I've also started using flashcards during class discussions."</i> MRF</p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More Careful 	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hands-on Activities 	<p><i>"The policy has made me think more carefully about how I structure my lessons. I can't rely on visuals anymore, so I focus on creating more interactive and verbal activities."-MC</i></p> <p><i>"I've started using a lot of hands-on activities to replace visuals. I also incorporate more group work, where students can talk things through and learn from each other."-MC</i></p>
Theme 2: Preparation Time	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Find New/Creative Ways • Additional Time • More Strategic • More Planning 	<p><i>"One challenge is that it requires more preparation. I've had to come up with new ways to engage the students without relying on visuals, which can be time-consuming."-MA</i></p> <p><i>"One challenge has been the additional time required to prepare materials for teaching."-MRS</i></p> <p><i>"I've had to be more strategic. I spend more time finding ways to make lessons engaging without relying on visuals."-MRS</i></p> <p><i>"It's made me more creative. I spend more time planning how to make lessons engaging without visuals."-MVD</i></p>

Table 3 presents a synthesis of elementary teachers' narratives regarding how the Bare Walls Policy (BWP), as mandated by DepEd Order No. 21, s. 2023, has influenced their decision-making processes in planning and implementing lessons. Through thematic analysis of the qualitative interview data, the study aimed to understand the most important changes teachers have made in response to the visual restrictions imposed by the policy. The analysis highlights the adaptive strategies and reflections of educators as they navigate a classroom environment devoid of traditional visual learning aids. The results offer insight into how teachers restructured their approaches to instruction, materials preparation, and classroom interaction to meet the changes brought up by the BWP.

This also shows the themes on teachers' responses regarding the significant changes in their decision-making processes in planning and implementing lessons in consideration of the Bare Walls Policy. The two main themes that emerged from the narratives include (1) Teaching Approach and (2) Preparation Time. These themes reflect how the policy has reshaped instructional strategies and demanded greater creativity and intentionality in daily teaching routines.

SYNTHESIS AND THEMATIC DISCUSSION ON THE CHANGES OF DECISION-MAKING OF TEACHERS

Theme 1: Teaching Approach

This theme illustrates how the Bare Walls Policy (BWP) led teachers to become more intentional, creative, and interactive in their teaching. Codes such as Storytelling or Role-Playing, Hands-on Activities, and More Physical Materials reflect a significant pedagogical shift toward active learning strategies. With visual aids removed, teachers are compensating through increased use of verbal instruction, manipulatives, and group tasks. They are crafting lessons that emphasize student engagement through experiential learning, integrating tools like flashcards, physical objects, storytelling, and group collaboration to maintain clarity and student interest.

This shift aligns with the principles of Constructivist Learning Theory, which highlights the value of active, hands-on engagement in promoting meaningful learning. Supporting this perspective, Calik et al. (2023) found that instructional approaches grounded in constructivist principles—particularly those that allow learners to interact directly with concepts and build understanding through experience—significantly improve academic performance. Their meta-analysis underscores that when students construct knowledge through guided activities and reflective processing, deeper conceptual understanding is more effectively achieved.

Moreover, the adoption of small group activities and interactive lessons supports Vygotsky's sociocultural theory, especially the concept of scaffolding, where learners develop understanding through guided participation and collaborative learning. Contemporary research affirms that meaningful student-content interaction plays a crucial role in enhancing learning outcomes, particularly in settings that demand higher levels of self-regulation and adaptability. Al Mamun and Lawrie (2023) found that students' behavioral engagement with inquiry-based online learning modules significantly supports deeper learning, demonstrating that well-designed, learner-driven content can effectively promote sustained academic engagement. These responses reveal a reflective and adaptive decision-making process among educators, focused on maintaining instructional quality and engagement despite the limitations imposed by the BWP.

Theme 2: Preparation Time

This theme reflects the increased cognitive and logistical effort teachers must invest in lesson planning under the Bare Walls Policy (BWP). Codes like More Strategic, Additional Time, and Find Creative Ways highlight the expanded demands on teachers' time and energy. Teacher's report spending more time designing materials, preparing hands-on tools, and brainstorming novel ways to present abstract content.

This increased workload resonates with the concept of Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK) the nuanced understanding of how to effectively teach specific content to diverse learners. While originally conceptualized by Shulman, contemporary studies

reaffirm that teachers today must integrate content knowledge with dynamic pedagogical strategies to meet evolving instructional demands. Recent literature highlights those environmental constraints, such as the removal of visual aids, compel teachers to deepen their PCK through careful planning and inventive instructional design (Ayu, 2020). The BWP appears to prompt a reflective transformation in how teachers prepare, encouraging them to re-examine not only what they teach, but how they teach it fostering a more adaptive and learner-centered instructional mindset.

Table 4. Teachers' Suggestions for Improvement and Innovation

Themes	Codes	Sample Narratives
Theme 1: Allow Temporary Visuals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To Strike a Balance • To Help Complex Topics • To be Flexible • Use Removable Diagrams 	<p><i>"I think allowing temporary visuals during lessons could strike a balance."-MS</i></p> <p><i>"I think allowing temporary visuals during lessons would help, especially for complex topics."</i></p> <p><i>"There should be some flexibility, like allowing temporary displays or exempting certain age groups."-MVD</i></p> <p><i>"I think the policy will allow temporary visuals during lessons. For example, when teaching science or math, we could use diagrams for specific period, then take them down once the lesson is over. -MC</i></p>
Theme 2: Access to Varied Learning Materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital Tools • Laminated Charts or Flashcards • Flashcards or Digital Platforms • Laminated Cards or Interactive Materials 	<p><i>"Digital learning tool could also be a good addition-using projectors or tablets to show content without sticking posters to the walls." ...-MC</i></p> <p><i>"One suggestion would be to allow teachers to use laminated charts or flashcards. They're portable, easy to store, and don't take up much space."—MA</i></p> <p><i>"Yes, I think providing teachers with resources like flashcards, laminated materials, or access to digital platforms would be very helpful. More teacher training on adapting to this policy would also make a big difference."-MAE</i></p> <p><i>"I think providing teachers with additional resources, like laminated cards or interactive materials, could make teaching</i></p>

		<i>easier. Training on alternative teaching strategies would also be helpful."-MT</i>
Theme 3: Reskilling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> More Training to Adapt Effectively Alternative Teaching	<i>"More training for teachers on how to adapt effectively and access to resources like projectors or interactive boards."-MS</i> <i>"More training on alternative teaching methods and access to digital resources would be great. Collaborative activities and peer learning strategies have also worked well for me."-MRS</i>

Table 4 presents a synthesis of the suggestions shared by teacher-participants regarding how the Bare Walls Policy (BWP) can be improved or innovated to enhance the learning climate. Their responses were gathered through qualitative interviews and thematically analyzed to address the research question: What innovations can be proposed to enrich the learning climate under the Bare Walls Policy? The insights offered by the participants reflect their adaptability, resourcefulness, and commitment to maintaining effective teaching and learning practices in a visually minimalist classroom environment.

This outlines the three major themes that emerged from teacher suggestions: (1) Allow Temporary Visuals, (2) Access to Varied Learning Materials, and (3) Reskilling. These themes underscore a collective effort by educators to find balanced, innovative strategies that align with the policy's intent while also responding to the practical needs of both teachers and learners. The themes reflect a nuanced understanding of the teaching process and advocate for flexibility, resource accessibility, and professional development.

SYNTHESIS AND THEMATIC DISCUSSION ON TEACHERS' SUGGESTION FOR IMPROVEMENT AND INNOVATION

Theme 1: Allow Temporary Visuals

This theme reflects the teachers' consensus that a flexible approach to visual aids could greatly improve lesson delivery, especially for complex topics. Codes like "To Strike a Balance", "To Help Complex Topics", and "Use Removable Diagrams" suggest that teachers are not opposed to the policy's intent but advocate for moderated implementation. Temporary visual aids—such as diagrams during science and math lessons—can support understanding without violating the spirit of the policy.

This aligns with research by Marzano (2007), who emphasizes that visual representations enhance student understanding, particularly for complex and abstract content. The flexibility to use visuals temporarily maintains student engagement while preserving the classroom's minimalist design outside of instructional time.

Theme 2: Access to Varied Learning Materials

Teachers also emphasized the importance of diverse and portable educational resources, including flashcards, laminated charts, digital tools, and interactive platforms. These suggestions reveal an interest in mobile and flexible alternatives to static wall displays. Teachers noted the benefits of using projectors, tablets, and other tools that do not contradict the BWP's guidelines but still provide the necessary instructional support.

This reflects the principles of Universal Design for Learning (UDL), which advocates for providing multiple means of representation to accommodate diverse learning styles (CAST, 2018). Using portable or digital materials helps teachers address individual learning differences while adhering to policy restrictions.

Theme 3: Reskilling

The final theme highlights the need for professional development through training and reskilling. Codes like More Training to Adapt Effectively and Alternative Teaching show that teachers are open to change but require institutional support to fully align their practices with the policy. The call for training on interactive teaching methods, collaborative learning, and use of digital resources underlines the importance of equipping teachers with the tools and strategies necessary to succeed in a bare-walled environment.

According to Darling-Hammond et al. (2017), effective professional development is essential for meaningful educational reform. Training programs that focus on innovative pedagogy, adaptive technologies, and student-centered practices are vital for successful policy implementation.

DISCUSSION

The Bare Walls Policy influences the change of the learning climate in a classroom, hence, affecting the social, cultural, psychological, and emotional aspects of the learning environment.

The research focuses on exploring the experiences, perceptions, and narratives of teachers regarding the implementation of DepEd Order No.21, s.2023, specifically the bare walls policy. The study will investigate how bare walls affect learning climate within classrooms, Qualitative methods particularly narrative inquiry will be employed to gather in-depth data, allowing for rich descriptions and interpretations of participants experiences.

This narrative inquiry was made up of five steps. These steps were not linear but overlapping and repetitive. The first step was determining whether the research problems best fit a narrative inquiry. The second step was selecting the individuals who have stories to tell and have the ability to participate in in-depth interviews. Data gathering instruments were adopted and crafted. They underwent validation by expert Eight participants were

included in the data gathering. The third step was collecting the data about the participants. Prior to the conduct of the interviews, informed consent was secured from the participants. In-depth interviews were then conducted. The fourth step was analyzing the results. This includes transcribing the interviews and restoring the narratives of the participants. The last step is interpreting the findings this includes making codes and themes on the story line of each participant that would answers on the research questions and objectives. The codes and themes were validated by an expert and also with the eight participants.

Findings

This section presents the results of the study on teachers' perceptions of the Bare Walls Policy (DepEd Order No. 21, s. 2023), its effects on students' learning behavior, the changes it brought to teachers' decision-making processes, and the suggestions for improving its implementation. The findings are organized according to the specific objectives of the study, covering teachers' perceptions, the observable impacts on students, the adjustments made by teachers in instructional planning, and the recommended innovations aligned with the policy.

- 1. Teachers' perceptions of the Bare Walls Policy revealed varied yet recurring viewpoints across participants.** The majority of teachers expressed that the policy required a significant shift in their instructional practices, particularly in handling younger learners who depend heavily on visual aids for comprehension and engagement. While some teachers recognized the policy's intention to reduce distractions and promote focus, many believed that the lack of visual materials made lessons more difficult to deliver effectively. Several teachers also acknowledged certain benefits, such as increased attentiveness among some learners, yet emphasized that these advantages did not outweigh the reduced engagement and the instructional limitations brought by the policy. Overall, teachers viewed the policy as well-intentioned but too rigid, leading to challenges in instruction, especially in the lower grade levels.
- 2. The impact of the Bare Walls Policy on students' learning behavior produced three dominant patterns based on teacher narratives.** First, students demonstrated increased classroom interaction, as they relied more on discussions with peers and teachers in the absence of visual cues. Second, the policy generated mixed effects on student attention and interest. Some students became more focused due to fewer distractions, while others—particularly visual learners—showed decreased engagement and reduced enthusiasm during lessons. Third, teachers reported that the policy made it harder for students to learn complex and abstract topics, especially in subjects such as Science and Mathematics, where visual representations are essential for understanding. These results show that while the policy may foster attentiveness for some learners, it also poses obstacles to comprehension and sustained interest.

3. **Changes in teachers' decision-making processes reflected two major areas of adjustment.** First, teachers shifted their teaching approaches by adopting more interactive, creative, and student-centered strategies to compensate for the absence of visual aids. They relied more on verbal explanations, demonstrations, and collaborative tasks to maintain student engagement. Second, teachers reported increased preparation time due to the need to redesign lessons and create movable or alternative instructional materials that comply with the policy. These changes highlight how the Bare Walls Policy influenced instructional planning and required teachers to seek new ways to support understanding without traditional classroom visuals.
4. **The suggestions for improvement and innovation offered by teachers identified three key themes related to policy enhancement.** The first theme emphasized allowing the use of temporary visuals during lessons to support comprehension, especially when teaching complex topics. Teachers believed that removable visual aids would strike a balance between compliance and instructional effectiveness. The second theme focused on providing access to varied learning materials such as digital tools, projectors, tablets, laminated cards, interactive flashcards, and other portable resources that do not violate the policy but still assist learning. The third theme underscored the importance of reskilling teachers through training on alternative teaching strategies, digital integration, and adaptive instructional methods. These suggestions reflect teachers' desire for a more flexible, supportive, and pedagogically aligned implementation of the policy.

Conclusions

The implementation of the Bare Walls Policy (DepEd Order No. 21, s. 2023) brought about significant shifts in teaching practices, classroom environments, and learning dynamics. Teachers' perceptions toward the policy varied, revealing a tension between understanding the intent to reduce distractions and the concern over its practicality—especially for young and visual learners. While some educators recognized potential benefits such as increased student focus and classroom discipline, many expressed frustrations regarding diminished engagement and creativity due to the absence of visual aids. These perceptions reflect a call for flexibility and contextual consideration in implementing the policy.

In terms of students' learning behavior, findings showed a complex picture. On the one hand, the policy encouraged more student-to-student and student-to-teacher interaction, as learners could no longer passively rely on wall visuals for support. On the other hand, it negatively impacted interest and engagement for many, particularly visual learners, and made comprehension of abstract topics more difficult. The reduced stimulation in classrooms lessened excitement and, for some students, confidence, thereby affecting both attention and retention.

The policy also led to notable changes in the decision-making process of teachers. Educators adapted by shifting toward more interactive and hands-on approaches such as

storytelling, group activities, and the use of manipulatives. However, this adaptation came with an increased burden of preparation time and the need to be more intentional and strategic in lesson planning.

Teachers proposed practical innovations to balance policy compliance with pedagogical effectiveness. These included allowing temporary or removable visuals during lessons, providing access to digital tools and laminated materials, and offering training for alternative teaching strategies. These suggestions highlight the educators' willingness to align with the policy's goals if given the tools and flexibility to do so effectively.

The implementation of the Bare Walls Policy (DepEd Order No. 21, s. 2023) has led to notable changes in the learning climate of classrooms, confirming the assumption that it affects the social, cultural, psychological, and emotional dimensions of the learning environment.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are suggested for consideration based on the study's conclusions and findings:

- 1. Integrate Flexibility into Policy Implementation.** The Department of Education may consider revising the Bare Walls Policy to incorporate flexibility that supports instructional effectiveness. Allowing the use of temporary or lesson-specific visual aids such as removable diagrams, flashcards, magnetic boards, or laminated materials during class can sustain learner engagement without compromising the policy's minimalist intent. Moreover, adaptation guidelines may be tailored according to learner age groups and subject complexity, ensuring that younger learners and subjects requiring conceptual visualization receive appropriate support.
- 2. Provide Access to Portable and Digital Learning Resources.** Schools may invest in portable and digital tools that allow teachers to use visual resources without violating wall display restrictions. Projectors, tablets, interactive boards, and other retractable or digital devices can provide dynamic instructional content while maintaining compliance with the policy. Additionally, distributing reusable learning materials such as laminated charts, flashcards, and portable activity kits can enhance visual and tactile learning without altering classroom walls.
- 3. Strengthen Teacher Training and Pedagogical Support.** The Department of Education may conduct professional development programs focused on alternative pedagogical strategies that align with the Bare Walls Policy. Training may include interactive approaches such as storytelling, role-playing, group activities, and the use of manipulatives or real-life objects. Collaborative learning techniques may also be promoted to build on the increased learner interaction observed under the policy. Furthermore, teachers may be provided with planning

templates, activity banks, or co-teaching support to help manage the additional preparation time required.

4. **Establish Continuous Monitoring and Policy Evaluation.** DepEd and school administrators may create formal feedback mechanisms to regularly assess the policy's impact on teaching and learning. Classroom observations, teacher consultations, and learner assessments may be used to determine whether the policy supports student comprehension and engagement. Documenting successful practices from schools or teachers who have effectively implemented the Bare Walls Policy can serve as helpful models for other institutions adjusting to the guidelines.
5. **Promote a Balanced and Inclusive Learning Environment.** The Department of Education may refine the policy to ensure that it accommodates the diverse learning modalities of students. A multimodal instructional approach—incorporating oral instruction, kinesthetic activities, flexible visuals, and interactive techniques—may be encouraged so that visual learners are not placed at a disadvantage. Balancing the minimalist classroom setup with inclusive teaching strategies can help sustain both focus and accessibility for all learners.

Proposed Action Plan: Enhancing the Implementation of the Bare Walls Policy (BWP)

Goal	Strategies	Activities	Responsible Person / Groups	Timeline	Expected Outcomes
1. Integrate Flexibility in Policy Implementation	Allow temporary visual Aids posted on a wall	Developed and disseminate guidelines on acceptable use of temporary/removable visual aids that can be posted on the wall.	DepEd Central and Regional Offices	Q1(Next School Year)	Teachers can use visuals without violating BWP
	Context-Specific Adaptation	Adjust implementation by grade level and subject complexity	Curriculum Developers, School Heads	Q1-Q2	Policy becomes responsive to learner needs.
2. Provide access to Portable and Digital Learning Resources.	Equip Classrooms with Digital Tools	Distribute Projectors, tablets, or interactive boards to schools.	DepEd ICT Unit, LGUs, School Heads	Q2-Q3	Digital visual enhance comprehension without violating BWP
	Distribute laminated and Reusable Materials	Create BWP-Complaint flashcards, charts, kits for hands-on use	Instructional Materials Developers, Regional Offices	Q2	Improved tactile and visual learning experience
3. Reskill and Support Teachers through	Training on alternative pedagogies	Conduct Workshops on storytelling, group work, realia-based teaching	Teachers training Institutions, Regional Officers	Q1-Q3	Teachers implement engaging visual Independent Strategies

Professional Development	Collaborative Learning Strategies	Integrate peer interaction strategies into training modules	DepEd Trainers, Master Teachers	Q2–Q4	Increased student collaboration and engagement
	Time Management Support	Provide planning templates and sample activity banks	DepEd Curriculum Division	Q2	Reduced teacher workload; enhanced planning quality
4. Monitor and Evaluate Policy	Feedback Loops	Conduct biannual surveys and focus group discussions with teachers	School Heads, Division Offices	Every Semester	Real-time feedback guides policy refinement
	Case Study Documentation	Identify and publish best practices from model schools	DepEd Research Unit, Principals	Annually	Shared models encourage effective adaptation across schools
5. Promote a Balanced, Multimodal Approach	Equity in Learning Modalities	Promote flexible visuals, kinesthetic tools, and oral instruction	Promote flexible visuals, kinesthetic tools, and oral instruction	Curriculum Developers, DepEd Policy Makers	All learning styles supported; inclusive classrooms created

Monitoring & Evaluation

- Quarterly Reports from schools on BWP adaptation and impact
- Annual Policy Review to incorporate feedback and revise implementation guidelines
- Classroom Observations by school heads and master teachers

Compliance with Ethical Consideration

The study strictly adhered to ethical standards to protect the rights and welfare of all participants. Permission was obtained from the school authorities, and informed consent was secured from the eight (8) Kindergarten to Grade 6 teachers of Del Pilar Elementary School, with participation being entirely voluntary and the right to withdraw at any time emphasized. Confidentiality and anonymity were maintained throughout the research process, with personal information removed from all data, which were used solely for academic purposes and stored securely. These measures ensured that the study respected participants' privacy, upheld their dignity, and maintained the highest standards of ethical integrity.

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